

Implementation of an operational ground based remote-sensing network and the search for end users: Experiences at the Slovenian Environment Agency

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Scope of the document

The aim of this document is to describe how the Slovenian Environment Agency became interested in atmospheric ground based remote sensing using different technologies (lidar, sodar,...) and how being part of international community provided benefits for the Agency itself and external users. This document, summarising the experience of a particular institute, might be useful as a starting point to other agencies. It helps to improve the WG1 deliverable D1.1 (List of identified relevant stakeholders) and D1.2 (Report on user-requirements from different stakeholders). It further contributes to task T1.1 (Identify weaknesses hampering exploitation of ABL profiling by end-users) and informs deliverable D1.3 (Recommendations for addressing the weaknesses identified in T1.1).

Graphical abstract: the timeline of the showcase

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1. A new ground-based remote sensing network

The Slovenian Environment Agency (SEA) operates an established, automatic meteorological surface synoptic network and weather radar network. The main meteorological synoptic stations, modernised 10 years ago, include also ceilometers (Vaisala CL31) that provide cloud-base height and cloudiness. Here, we outline how the SEA extended its observations by implementing a new network of ground-based remote sensing profile instruments.

1.1. STEP I: Main motivations and funding

During an air-quality EU funded project for which SEA management successfully applied for and started in 2016, the SEA air-quality department (AQD) provided requirements for new modelling tools. Additionally, new profile measurements were needed for dispersion modelling and to gain deeper understanding of the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) processes that influence air-quality local dynamics and long-range transport in complex and opened terrains. The experience of a senior scientist working at the AQD provided the impulse to include ground base based remote sensing instruments in the project proposal. The Sodar (*sound detection and ranging*) and Rass (*radio acoustic sounding system*) technology is well proven and was considered as one of the main candidates.

1.2. STEP II: Market analysis

The SEA department for Atmospheric Remote Sensing (ARS) carried out the market analysis, to assess which instruments were most suitable to gather the information on ABL variables. As the field of exact applications was not finalised at this stage, the following general criteria were first identified to guide the informed decision making process (budget constraints as well as more specific requirements were considered at a later stage, see Sect. 1.5):

- data that can be obtained from the sensor and field of application
- user friendliness of operation
- maintenance and support
- configuration of a sensor
- set-up and mobility of a sensor
- uncertainty of measurements
- calibration
- data formats
- availability of data processing tools
- quality procedures
- existing EU or national wide standardised measuring framework

As an operational meteorological office we needed to have instruments that are already recognized and used in the user community, like national meteorological offices. User friendliness is also a very important factor since there is very little space left for research, we need sensors that can operate 24/7.

After the first discussion within SEA on the user needs which provided us with a rough estimate of the parameters, like wind and temperature profiles, our department carried out an intense online search for documents on ABL, mixing height, atmospheric remote sensing, ground based remote sensors, lidars, sodars, etc. That has led us to different research publishing web portals where we have found many articles about the subject of ground based remote sensing and got an overview about how this field developed during the years. We built a database of people, articles, publications and institutions that were or used to be active in the field.

One of the first interesting publications we found was the book by Stefan Emeis “*Surface-based remote sensing, of the atmospheric boundary layer*” which gives a good overview of the topic from basic physical concepts to potential applications. Later on the PROBE publications and videos provided more insight. We have also inspected the documents from the previous projects and actions, such as:

- COST 715 – Urban meteorology applied to air pollution problems
- COST 720 – Integrated ground based remote sensing stations for atmospheric profiling
- ES0702 – European ground based observations of essential variables from climate and operational meteorology (EG-CLIMET)
- ES1303 – Towards operational ground based profiling with ceilometers, Doppler lidars and microwave radiometers for improving weather forecasts (TOPROF)

The first market sweep provided us with lots of different instruments from lidars, Doppler lidars, radiometer, sodars, rass, pulsed lidars, raman lidars, etc.

At first we were lacking knowledge on the subject, so we were addressing the sensor market according to the web and expo marketing strategies of different companies. We could have been convinced to buy some sensor in a way we buy consumer electronics. But having done some projects before, we knew that we have to compare the sensors available on the market according to our demands. The experiences with a surface network upgrade project few years ago helped us a lot.

So we addressed the market in a similar way as we did for the surface network. In this second more specific survey we compared:

- output data
- measuring ranges
- uncertainty of the output data
- mobility of the sensor
- sensor technology
- vertical resolution
- compliance to national regulatory laws
- sensitivity to environmental conditions like fog, rain, sound, high frequency communication links, temperature, humidity and wind
- prices

The name of the company also provided us with some info about the quality of the sensor on the market. What we did not really know was the **readiness** of the technology since one can pack a technology into a nice box and sell it as a maintenance free product. We knew a lot about the market and technologies of the surface meteorological network and weather radar network but the ground based profiling sensor market was really a new field for us.

This is where the E-PROFILE and PROBE community with knowledge transfer by means of meetings and documents provided us with the information on what types of sensors are appropriate for the operational agency.

1.3. STEP III: Engagement with European community

The ARS department contacted professional actors working in the field of ground-based atmospheric profile remote sensing from academia and research institutions to instrument operators and national meteorological offices. We have also established contacts with different manufacturers.

In this period we were already in contact with people from two active international programs (E-PROFILE, PROBE). The contacts came through regular channels of EUMETNET and our national representatives. Becoming part of this community enabled us to not only look at the instruments from a high-end user point of view but also to gain basic understanding of the details concerning measurement techniques and uncertainties intrinsic to each type of instrument, advanced processing tools and standard data formats. Email correspondence and on-line video meetings with the international community was very helpful during both market analysis and measurement network implementation.

Since the PROBE community was in the process of analysing the maturity of particular instruments and finding that some are ready to be deployed in the operational user community, this moment was really suitable for us.

The first document from PROBE that was important for us, was Cimini et al. (2022). It provided us with an overview on how to participate and how to profit from the action and international community. The process of understanding how the international community works took us some time. Publications, video tutorials and zoom meetings in combination with a very good communication agenda and web page of the PROBE action enabled efficient transfer of know-how at different levels: from organisational perspective, overviews about sensors and technologies to processing and integration of national dataflow into international platforms, which was addressed by E-PROFILE.

The “Joint WG3/WG4 [document](#) on the overview of European ground based remote sensing networks” helped us with gaining overview of sensors and capabilities which we could later on communicate to our end-users when asked for details about the subject.

1.4. STEP IV: Discussion of market analysis results

Results of the market analysis were presented continuously to the internal end-users of our agency (air quality and NWP) and management and their feedback was taken into account. During this iterative process, the users were able to formulate increasingly clearly their needs and specific requirements (such as the need for observations during fog which can not be achieved by certain sensor types). Our ARS department led the discussion by presenting the market of ground based remote sensing sensors to the colleagues and explaining to them the basic technical concepts of different sensors, data outputs and uncertainty, complexity of the sensors and prices. The decision process about what sensors to buy was on the one hand constrained by the budget, and on the other hand there was a need for measurements availability in all types of weather. Last but not least, mobility of the sensors was also an important parameter.

We have synchronised the user needs (measured variables, environmental conditions, temporal resolution, vertical resolution, maximum vertical range, etc.) and management budget constraints to come up with the final sensor list: sodar-rass, automated lidar-ceilometer and cwfm doppler lidar. We have understood that many European networks are nowadays focused on optical and microwave devices, but the demand for data in foggy conditions from air-quality department was defining our decision path. Finally we have decided to buy three different sensors to cover wind, temperature and aerosol profiles in different types of weather and to provide mobility to a certain extent.

The ARS department issued a report that was also presented to the Agency internal users and management that later on approved the final decision.

1.5. STEP V: Measurement network implementation

The new lidar-ceilometer and doppler-lidar sensors were placed at existing measurement sites of the SEA surface-station network. However, the sensor placement is flexible, according to the research and monitoring needs of different end users.

The sodar-rass system needed a different approach, since the acoustic sounding signal is in the range of hearing frequencies and is not possible to install the sodar near populated areas. We visited several potential sites. The Waste disposal facility was very open to cooperation and provided a location inside their enclosed area that was far away from residential areas. They also expressed interest in the data (see Sect. 2.3).

After the tender, we were busy with arranging the delivery of sensors which was additionally complicated by the fact that it was the time of the pandemic and travelling was very limited. Additional zoom sessions were organised by manufacturers to provide support and learning. The zoom sessions were recorded which is a real benefit in terms of training and knowledge transfer.

Again the knowledge we have obtained from the community helped us to better carry out the procedures of delivery and installation during the health crisis.

Finally, sensor installations were finished, and configuration was done under the supervision of manufacturers, but here also the knowledge gained from PROBE and E-PROFILE helped us to be proactive at the configuration procedures and not being only observers, because we already understood how the sensors are working and how they are used in other countries.

At present all three sensors are set-up and configured at different locations with data polling and processing chain built at the Agency with bash and Python 3 scripting to provide end users with numerical *netcdf* formatted data or visual products.

Picture 1: Profilers in the new ground based remote sensing network. From left to right: cwfm doppler lidar, CL51 and sodar-rass.

1.6. STEP VI: Advanced retrievals and products

At first the overview publications and videos at PROBE web page provided us with the starting point when setting up the network, later more specific topics, like ABL algorithms attracted our attention. Currently we are concentrating on different algorithms so we will hopefully in the future use them not as a black box, but as at least conceptually decoded packages.

First dataflow was built on bash and Python scripts, and partially by dedicated software packages of the sensors, like BLVCL51. Currently the dataflow does not incorporate advanced processing apart from CL51 Vaisala's BLView software. Our plan is to bypass BLView and do the processing by ourselves on a linux platform, but that is a task one needs additional time and resources for, which are normally limited.

Internationally coordinated platform for advanced products could provide the mechanism that many countries could benefit from. In that sense, the role of E-PROFILE providing a data hub and internationally accepted data calibration procedures and corrections for partners is of great value and importance.

Additionally we are involved in cooperation and plan later implementation of PARAFOG algorithm (IPSL - Institut Pierre Simon LaPlace) which has a large application potential for Aviation weather forecasting sector and possibly also for municipality heating energetics, Marine traffic and ports industrial sector.

2. Outreach and end-user engagement

To maximise usage of the observations gathered by the new ground based remote sensing network, the search for new end-users is being actively addressed. As end-user correspondence continues to give us a different view on the subject and specific needs of the users, these activities directly feed back into the concept of the measurement network and advanced data product retrievals.

2.1. Identification of end-users

The user identification process was started from the very beginning when we were scanning the market and preparing the grounds for deciding on what instrument to buy in terms of technology, sensors and operability.

Actually, one of our most important (internal) end-users, promoting also the purchase of new sensors-profilers was the Air quality department (AQD) at the Agency. The reason for this was that there was a know-how on the subject of remote sensing and air-quality applications at the department. In 70' and 80' there was a very important agenda to understand the meteorological impacts on the air quality in the complex terrain where factories were being built. At that time the sounding was done with balloons attached to the string with an electronics for temperature sensing and signal transmission. Later on in the 90' there was also a SODAR in the district of Ljubljana. So **existing experiences from senior scientists** and engineers paved the way to deciding on the need to buy remote sensing instruments since the product readiness of the marketed products was now high and suitable for operational work.

In the course of building the ground-based remote sensing network, we have been mostly in contact with Air quality department at the Agency, but later in the process when we have formed a more clear picture on the subject of ground based remote sensing in Europe, we started to contact potential other end-users.

The users were contacted either by direct conversation or by email. We were considering who could benefit from the ground based remote sensing data and when discussing the subject with one of the potential user a new user was identified. We were also contacted from the user's side, if users learned about us from others that we have already talked to, mostly inside our Agency. There were also events when some users realised that they could benefit from us, like local municipality that was considering an idea about a waste burning thermal plant in cooperation with the Waste disposal facility.

Two general groups of end-users are identified:

- 1) Departments inside the SEA
 - Air-quality modelling and forecasting for general public and as a regulatory advisory body
 - Numerical weather prediction
 - General weather forecasting office
 - Aviation weather forecasting office
- 2) Public and private sector outside the agency
 - Academia
 - Heating and electricity energetics
 - Sport events
 - Local municipality
 - Waste disposal facility
 - Private companies in the field of environmental monitoring and modelling
 - Marine traffic and ports sector with marine weather forecasting

Specific benefits of atmospheric profiling for each end-user group are described in detail in Sect. 2.3.

2.2. Outreach approach

The communication approach was different, depending on the area of user expertise and field of work.

The approach for users inside our Agency was more in-depth discussion based on physical principles of each sensors, data and possible basic products, but also mentioning some advanced products like mixing height (MH) and fog alerts (Parafog algorithm).

When we contacted people from different fields than physics or meteorology, we found that in-depth understanding of both their subjects and remote sensing potentials (see Sect. 2.4) is also of great importance. Equipped with knowledge we were more capable of **disseminating basic concepts and possible added values** to the end users using simpler language.

The first contacts with the end users were on one hand systematically triggered from our side. But during the course of events that led us to find the locations for some of the sensors, the mutual cooperation led to the interest for the data. For example sodar-rass system needed a location away from populated areas but still being representative of the regional environmental conditions. The cooperation with the Waste disposal facility was started from our side and brought also interest from their side, since they used to have sodar at their facility run by an external environmental company responsible for environmental measurements (see Sect. 2.3). The same environmental company is also active these days and we will provide them with data which will be used or analysed also by the Waste disposal facility. The use of data can be in daily operational mode or in case of potential accident, fire, etc.

Connecting via other stakeholders: End users from Hot air balloons sporting sector contacted us through the links with Aviation weather forecasting department. We have supported the World cup Hot air balloon competition to see how different cooperation can bring mutual benefits. The Hot air balloons touristic sector was addressed by national regulatory and supervisory agency for air traffic which approached us through Aviation weather forecasting office and asked us if we could provide regular wind profile data, since sodar-rass is situated near the flatlands landing area outside the capital of Ljubljana.

The gained knowledge gave us the capabilities to approach different users and discuss their needs or provide them with a possible final solutions for their field of work.

2.3. End-user expectations and feedbacks

- The different end user demands can sometimes be in conflict since there can be needs for the data at different locations, which cuts into the continuity of data at one site. So different user demands should be assessed and prioritised.
- What was common to some extent to both user groups is their expectation that what we can offer, is a user friendly tool offering clear interpretation that almost instantly shows its potentials and doesn't bring too much of a delay into routine work during the implementation phase.
- Part-time campaigns at different locations or continuous measurements at one location is something that must be addressed and was recognized by putting together different current end user needs.
- Data continuity with representing regional ABL and on the long term providing ABL climatology is also of high priority.
- Continuous data providing climatology of regional ABL is needed by air-quality and climatological departments. The former is using the data for modelling local micrometeorological conditions and air pollution in case of emission sources from industrial objects, the latter is using the long term data for assessing the potential for green energy, like wind farms.

Here we list some user-specific feedback that was collected.

Air-quality sector feedback:

- the need for wind profiles in the lower levels and also in low wind situations
- the need for inversion heights or mixing layer heights
- temperature profiles
- the need for data availability in conditions with fog
- assessing the ABL stability classes
- knowing the source of aerosols

Numerical weather prediction feedback:

- the need for 2D or 3D wind field for model validation or in case of a larger network assimilation
- temperature profiles are also interesting if they provide high-resolution temperature profiles for low level inversions or multiple inversion layers
- the presence of clouds as a future plan

General weather forecasting office feedback:

- wind and temperature profiles that provide the picture of dynamic of the ABL in situations like low level inversions or warm front over cold air pools
- backscatter profiles that provide the mixing layer height and give information about the presence of fog or low stratus
- information about the presence of supercooled droplets in the atmosphere for assessing the potential for freezing conditions on the ground
- thermodynamic instability for storm potential

Aviation weather forecasting office feedback:

- wind profiles for wind shear situations
- fog forecasting
- clear air turbulence at higher elevations
- presence of supercooled droplets in the atmosphere for assessing the freezing potential for aviation
- thermodynamic instability for storm potential

Local municipality feedbacks:

- providing the public with the environmental data at the urban scale
- scientific support of the project of waste burning power plant with the use of ground based remote sensing instrument to provide information on the climatology of inversion heights, strengths and duration

Waste disposal facility feedbacks:

- wind profile and temperature profile data for analysing smell issues in different weather situations and predicting the dispersion of pollutants in case of an accident
- evaluation of mixing layer height is also important in accessing possible concentrations of dispersed pollutants

Sports sector feedbacks:

- Hot air balloons competition sector uses the data for regional low level wind conditions
- Hot air balloons touristic sector is also interested in providing continuous wind profiles for the area of lowlands near the capital city where the launching or landing mostly takes place

Experiences with Nuclear power plants:

- this sector is very rigid and strictly regulated so they have their own remote sensing sensors for providing them with wind and temperature profiles data for evaluating the potential spread of emissions in case of an accident

Experiences with Energetics:

- the sector really knows what they want and you have to provide them persuasive end-user products that clearly show their potential
- we still think we could convince them that the new ground based remote sensing data can be beneficial to them
- two sections are considered: heating and electricity

Experiences with Industry:

- industrial objects are obliged by law to provide monitoring for their emissions so the mobile sensors could be set to provide real time and continuous data for a sufficient period of time to assess the micrometeorological conditions in complex terrains that influence the potential pollution

Experiences with Academia:

- they have proposals for cooperation at the data analysis level for masters or doctorate theses
- they expressed the need for mixing layer height for research applications on the subject of air pollution and estimation of emission sources strength

Private companies in the field of environmental monitoring and modelling:

- some of the companies we have contacted did not engage in the cooperation with PROBE
- currently there is one company that shows great interest on the subject and is also an external contracting provider of environmental monitoring data for Waste disposal facility

2.4. The role of expertise

To convince new stakeholders of the benefits provided by the new data products, a certain expertise is required. The ARS department is gaining increasing experience with the sensors, data and retrievals. The process is supported by knowledge exchange with E-PROFILE and PROBE. The following aspects are beneficial:

- Realisation that there is an initiative for an operational pan EU network of profilers
- Understanding how the international community is organised
- Knowledge on the workings of the sensors: ALC, DWL, MWR
- Knowledge on the user friendliness of each technology and sensors
- Knowledge on the sensor specific calibration and correction procedures needed
- Information on the advanced processing products and possible application
- Experiences with sensors and tools from different institutes or organisations
- Information about the impact of different sensor networks on the model performance
- Information on the urban scale activities and current knowledge of the urban ABL structure and dynamics

The understanding of the “big picture” from technical details and working concepts of different technologies to calibration procedures, processing algorithms and finally pan European frameworks (ex. E-PROFILE) organisation, has given us a firm basis when communicating to private sector and to institutions outside of our Agency.

2.5. Materials or accessory tools to showcase benefits and applications

To communicate benefits of the new data products to potential end-users it is absolutely essential to explain the basic concept in a suitable language and to have applied showcase illustrations that highlight the measurement capabilities and impact.

That is where E-PROFILE and PROBE community provided a very good platform for sharing knowledge through video tutorials, working and sub working groups, on-line meetings and literature. All of that clearly accessible through the main action web page <https://www.probe-cost.eu>.

2.6. Catalyst events

One example of an important step in users expressing the need for the new data after the network was in operation, was a few days dropout of radiosonde data due to technical issues. Some of the visualisation products became interesting for the users (General and Aviation weather forecasting office) and our department has taken this radiosonde dropout as a chance to promote the ABL data to the SEA internal end users.

A similar effect of a sudden increase in interest for the profile data can occur during specific atmospheric events (e.g. smoke advected from wildfires).

3. Short-term and long-term plans

With the new knowledge and experiences gained through the international community of PROBE and with work done to start-up a new ground based remote-sensing network, we can now address further steps aligned with the end users community that we have contact with: air-quality, NWP, general forecasting, aviation forecasting, energetic sector, urban municipalities and sports sector.

There is an ongoing process of “rolling review of requirements” that drives the operational network development and organisation, including data processing and new user products.

Currently recognized goals:

- updating the code for dataflow
- updating the code for data visualisation
- set-up dataflow of ALCs to E-PROFILE
- develop supervisory software application for basic overview of sensors meta data which show the status of sensors
- expand existing network with one or two more sensors to reach the limit of what we can maintain and support in order to cover both user types: providing long-term data and doing shorter measuring campaigns
- reconfigure existing CL31s from surface synoptic network to provide backscatter signal and integrate them into newly implemented ground based remote sensing dataflow scheme
- gather end-user needs and arrange them according to priorities given by the SEA’s short and long term plans that address the field of ground based remote sensing
- organise internal workshop for the users or newly identified users
- define a document form for more systematic exchange of end users needs
- search for new users and try to agree on the level of cooperation with the academia institutions
- work on the recognition of importance of the ground based remote sensing field
- new human resources

4. Conclusions

We have made a big step from where we were just a few years ago and are currently moving from implementation to operational level. Few years ago we would not have considered a new network. An EU co-funded project, experiences from senior scientist and support from the management gave us the push to establish a small new network of ground based remote sensing sensors. Looking back, we are now able to see what has been done and which steps have led us to the current level of operability of the newly set-up ground based remote-sensing network. Here we summarise a few key lessons learned during the process:

- Ground based remote sensing sensors can not be considered as “plug-and-play” devices but present a **challenging new field of measurements** that is constantly evolving.
- Due to the advanced measurement setup and data products, the new network requires a considerable amount of **human resources**. A certain expertise and experience is required to adequately process the data, implement higher-level processing tools and to interpret the results and their uncertainties.
- Being part of the **international community** has broadened our view and enlarged our know-how on the subject which in turn produced positive feedback on the development of the new

network. The know-how gathered from PROBE was important for in-depth communication with the manufacturers asking them scientific questions and not just buying a black box.

- It is interesting to reflect on the viewpoint of different users and how their view on what ground based remote-sensing data can bring to them changed through **time**. Multiple attempts to discuss the data and “brainstorm” with the potential users on the applicability slowly produced results. Also mentioning that other big meteorological offices are actively advancing in the field of ground based remote sensing added importance to discussion.
- SEA Department for Atmospheric Remote Sensing (ARS) actively addressed specific users repeatedly. The process continues and we normally need to be familiarised with the specific field that we find interesting as a potential end user. Having enough background knowledge from the ground-based remote sensing field and understanding basic targeted user needs, we can discuss potential applications. Here **examples and showcases** are of great importance. Finding engaged end users and useful applications is what provides us with the arguments when communicating to the management the resources needed.
- A good thing when addressing the end users was that we were proactive because end users at different levels of ground based remote sensing measuring and processing chain have different affinity to the subjects and understand **different terminology**, so one needs to use different words, and pictures are of great help when trying to transfer a new field of data and products to potential new user. Asking them questions from their field of work or reading a basic article about the work they do, gave us a broader view when communicating possible applications from ground based remote sensing network with them.
- The type of organisation of public sector, like many important users being under the umbrella of the same Agency, was beneficial to ARS department, since we used **personal approach** to engage the end-users. Also some external users were approached by means of former acquaintances or knowing that some colleagues from student days are working in an area of private sector. At the moment external users are not highly engaged and we will approach them with more systematic tools, like organised presentations of the showcases to management, middle-management or operational departments of companies and other public Agencies. We have also identified new potential user groups in Marine industry sector.
- The PROBE **video recordings** of meetings and dedicated tutorials are a very good approach when communicating the knowledge to someone. In this way one can replay a video on the subject many times which improves the efficiency of knowledge transfer.

The interested reader is advised to look at **Appendix A** for a more detailed description of interactions with end users. **Appendix B** and a **journey diagram** summarise the necessary steps of the whole process from a more general perspective.

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